

Ten simple actions to make NanoSafety Cluster Research Output more Findable

Egon Willighagen <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7542-0286>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10533126>

A lot is written about the FAIR principles for making data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (just [search for FAIR “NanoSafety Cluster” in Google Scholar](#)). But the NanoSafety Cluster (NSC) is putting these things into practice. This document describes a few solutions adopted by the NSC that can be used by any NSC project partner. Here, we widen the focus from data to research output, as proposed by Houweling¹. We can even push this all the way to make NSC projects themselves more FAIR, as described in this newsletter in 2018². To me, this is important, as a lot of nanosafety knowledge is not easily captured in raw numbers. The integration of data sources to support nanosafety research was identified by several initiatives³.

Findable in Zenodo

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface for the NanoSafety Cluster. The top navigation bar includes the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. The user profile 'egon.willig...' is visible. Below the navigation bar, the 'EU NanoSafety Cluster' is identified, with a 'New upload' button. The main content area shows search results for 'Records', with 219 results found. The results are sorted by 'Newest'. The first result is 'Visum Particle - QuickStart Guide' by IRIS Technology, Gomez, Susana; Urrego, Carlos, uploaded on January 10, 2024. The second result is 'A control system solution to SAfety BY Design Of nanoMAterials // SbD4Nano e-infrastructure for performance testing & implementation of SbD approaches in the nanotechnology supply chain' by Alfaro Serrano, Beatriz; Steenson, Karen; Resch, Susanne; and 1 other, uploaded on June 11, 2023. The interface includes filters for 'Versions', 'Access status', and 'Resource types'.

To get a globally unique identifier for research output can easily be done with the digital object identifier (DOI). DOIs are routinely minted by NSC projects using [Figshare](#) and [Zenodo](#), not just for data, but also the NSC Newsletter and project deliverables. Zenodo is of particular interest here because of the integration with the EU CORDIS database and the [Zenodo NSC Community](#). The link with the CORDIS database links the research output to the EU grant, while the second makes it easier to find output from other NSC projects.

Action 1

Get a DOI for your research output; it is by far the easiest way to make your work more FAIR.

Action 2

If your NSC project does not have a Zenodo Community, encourage your project coordinator to create one. Example communities exist for the three [Nano Risk Governance](#) projects, [NanoSolveIT](#), [NanoCommons](#), and [SbD4Nano](#).

Action 3

Link your research output on Zenodo to at least the [NSC Community](#).

Findable on the NSC Website

The screenshot shows the NanoSafety Cluster website. The header includes the logo and navigation links: Overview, NSC Projects, Cooperation, Outputs, News & Activities, Contact, and a search icon. The main content area is titled 'Overview' and contains the following text:

This page provides available knowledge from the nanosafety community, as produced by projects and published through public deliverables and peer reviewed publications. In due course, the NSC aims to also provide links to publicly available datasets, analysis tools and software.

If you upload your publication to Zotero, please link it to the [NSC group in Zotero](#). This way, your publication will automatically be added to the list below.

If you would like an article, report, public deliverable or other publication to be added to the list, please send the DOI and the publication URL to info@nanosafetycluster.eu. If your resource does not have a DOI you can either acquire one for free from [Zenodo](#). If you upload your publication to Zenodo, please do not forget to link it to the [NSC Community in Zenodo](#).

NOTE: the list of deliverables and publications below is not complete.

575 Publications

Deliverables and publications

2023

1. Wyrzykowska E, Swirog M. Influence of protein corona on cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles against human keratinocyte cell line (HaCaT) [Internet]. Zenodo; 2023 [cited 2023 Nov 22]. Available from: <https://zenodo.org/record/8297121> (CITE)
2. Wyrzykowska E, Swirog M. Identification of factors determining the process of aggregation/agglomeration of

The DOI makes it possible for other efforts to propagate the metadata of the research output. For example, [DataCite](#) indexes output in Figshare and Zenodo⁴. The NanoSafety Cluster also keeps track of research output on their website (see the above screenshot). For this, it keeps a [Zotero group](#) of data, journal articles, and project deliverables, assuming they have DOIs. The content of this library is embedded as a publication list on the NSC website. The NSC collected more than 500 journal articles (the oldest from 2010), 55 datasets, and 37 project deliverables, knowing this is just a subset of the full output of the cluster.

Action 4

Therefore, we welcome submission of more DOIs. Instructions on how to send DOIs for data, articles, deliverables, etc, to the NSC cluster can be found at nanosafetycluster.eu/outputs/public-deliverables-publications/.

Findable based on JRC and ERM identifiers

But if we can go beyond sharing the main metadata of the output (title, authors, venue, publication date), then we realize that this is just the start: we want to find research output about a particular (type of) nanomaterial. This is more interesting for risk assessment than finding all articles by some researcher, which undoubtedly misses much relevant literature. That is, we are just starting to realize how we want to find research output⁵.

Therefore, when you get a DOI for research output, use nanomaterial identifiers clearly in the research output or even as keywords. The latter was recently done by a NanoSolveIT partner⁶. Identifiers that can be used include the identifiers for the JRC representative industrial nanomaterials⁷ and the European Registry of Materials identifier⁸. The InChI for nanomaterials (NInChI) is still under development and may not yet be persistent⁹.

The *Research Output management, FAIRness & sharing* working group (formerly, WGF and WG4) has activities to propagate metadata of research output about nanomaterials. Particularly, these two projects started under the [NanoCommons](#) project: one project tracks journal articles about the JRC materials; the second tracks citable datasets with open licenses:

- [Ontology IRIs for the JRC representative industrial nanomaterials](#) (see Action 6)
- [Overview of open datasets released by NanoSafety Cluster projects](#) (see Action 7)

Both websites make use of [Bioschemas](#) standards which are supported by major search engines like Google Search. For example, by listing datasets in the overview, they automatically become visible in the [Google Dataset Search](#).

Action 5

Use nanomaterial identifiers clearly in research output and ideally as keywords.

Action 6

If you find your research article about JRC materials missing in the *JRC representative industrial nanomaterials* page, register the DOI with the NSC website (see Action 4).

Action 7

If you find your open-licensed dataset missing in the *Overview of open datasets*, email me the DOI.

Findable via ELIXIR

Elsewhere in this *NSC Updates*¹⁰ you will find an article on the [ELIXIR Toxicology Community](#), described in more detail in a recent *whitepaper*¹¹. The next three actions are simple solutions to make other types of research (project) output more findable: training material, computational services, standards. You do not have to be a member of the Toxicology Community to take these actions.

Action 8

Training material can be registered in the [ELIXIR TeSS platform](#), like [NanoCommons did too](#). You can log in via the LS Identifier using your ORCID.

Action 9

Computational services can be registered with the [ELIXIR bio.tools platform](#), and link your services to [the toxicology domain](#).

Action 10

Read the recipes in the ELIXIR-hosted [FAIR Cookbook](#)¹² which gives many more ideas on how to make your output more FAIR.

Conclusion

This article gives ten simple actions to make EU NanoSafety Cluster research output more findable using solutions adopted by the NSC (projects). Findable is a minimal step for making output more reusable (more FAIR) and at the very least supports our dissemination activities and exchange of knowledge about nanomaterial safety. For experimental nanosafety data, the sharing via community templates is coming along nicely^{13,14}. But I wish for a future where all NSC research output is made findable, whether open-licensed or not. The EU NanoSafety Cluster helps with this, beyond just data, but needs your input, as described by the ten actions.

References

- (1) Houweling, J.; Willighagen, E. Research Output Management. *Qeios* **2023**. <https://doi.org/10.32388/ZNWI7T>.
- (2) Willighagen, E.; Najko Jahn; Nielsen, F. Å. The EU NanoSafety Cluster as Linked Data Visualized with Scholia. *NSC Newsl.* **2018**, 470931 Bytes. <https://doi.org/10.6084/M9.FIGSHARE.6727931>.
- (3) Karcher, S.; Willighagen, E. L.; Rumble, J.; Ehrhart, F.; Evelo, C. T.; Fritts, M.; Gaheen, S.; Harper, S. L.; Hoover, M. D.; Jeliaskova, N.; Lewinski, N.; Marchese Robinson, R. L.; Mills, K. C.; Mustad, A. P.; Thomas, D. G.; Tsiliki, G.; Hendren, C. O. Integration among Databases and Data Sets to Support Productive Nanotechnology: Challenges and Recommendations. *NanoImpact* **2017**, 9, 85–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.impact.2017.11.002>.
- (4) Brase, J. DataCite - A Global Registration Agency for Research Data. In *2009 Fourth International Conference on Cooperation and Promotion of Information Resources in Science and Technology*; IEEE: Beijing, China, 2009; pp 257–261. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COINFO.2009.66>.
- (5) Ammar, A.; Bonaretti, S.; Winckers, L.; Quik, J.; Bakker, M.; Maier, D.; Lynch, I.; van Rijn, J.; Willighagen, E. A Semi-Automated Workflow for FAIR Maturity Indicators in the Life Sciences. *Nanomaterials* **2020**, 10 (10), 2068. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10102068>.
- (6) Knigge, Xenia; Radnik, Jörg. Physico-Chemical Characterization of Sterile Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticles by XPS / HAXPES / SEM, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7990302>.
- (7) Totaro, S.; Cotogno, G.; Rasmussen, K.; Pianella, F.; Roncaglia, M.; Olsson, H.; Riego Sintes, J. M.; Crutzen, H. P. The JRC Nanomaterials Repository: A Unique Facility Providing Representative Test Materials for nanoEHS Research. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* **2016**, 81, 334–340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2016.08.008>.
- (8) van Rijn, J.; Afantitis, A.; Culha, M.; Dusinska, M.; Exner, T. E.; Jeliaskova, N.; Longhin, E. M.; Lynch, I.; Melagraki, G.; Nymark, P.; Papadiamantis, A. G.; Winkler, D. A.; Yilmaz, H.; Willighagen, E. European Registry of Materials: Global, Unique Identifiers for (Undisclosed) Nanomaterials. *J. Cheminformatics* **2022**, 14 (1), 57. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-022-00614-7>.
- (9) Lynch, I.; Afantitis, A.; Exner, T.; Himly, M.; Lobaskin, V.; Doganis, P.; Maier, D.; Sanabria, N.; Papadiamantis, A. G.; Rybinska-Fryca, A.; Gromelski, M.; Puzyn, T.; Willighagen, E.; Johnston, B. D.; Gulumian, M.; Matzke, M.; Green Etxabe, A.; Bossa, N.; Serra, A.; Liampa, I.; Harper, S.; Tämm, K.; Jensen, A. C.; Kohonen, P.; Slater, L.; Tsoumanis, A.; Greco, D.; Winkler, D. A.; Sarimveis, H.; Melagraki, G. Can an InChI for Nano Address the Need for a

Simplified Representation of Complex Nanomaterials across Experimental and Nanoinformatics Studies? *Nanomaterials* **2020**, *10* (12), 2493. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10122493>.

- (10) Willighagen, E. The ELIXIR Toxicology Community. *NSC Updat.* **2024**. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10551071>.
- (11) Martens, M.; Stierum, R.; Schymanski, E. L.; Evelo, C. T.; Aalizadeh, R.; Aladjov, H.; Arturi, K.; Audouze, K.; Babica, P.; Berka, K.; Bessems, J.; Blaha, L.; Bolton, E. E.; Cases, M.; Damalas, D. E.; Dave, K.; Dilger, M.; Exner, T.; Geerke, D. P.; Grafström, R.; Gray, A.; Hancock, J. M.; Hollert, H.; Jeliaskova, N.; Jennen, D.; Jourdan, F.; Kahlem, P.; Klanova, J.; Kleinjans, J.; Kondic, T.; Kone, B.; Lynch, I.; Maran, U.; Martinez Cuesta, S.; Ménager, H.; Neumann, S.; Nymark, P.; Oberacher, H.; Ramirez, N.; Remy, S.; Rocca-Serra, P.; Salek, R. M.; Sallach, B.; Sansone, S.-A.; Sanz, F.; Sarimveis, H.; Sarntivijai, S.; Schulze, T.; Slobodnik, J.; Spjuth, O.; Tedds, J.; Thomaidis, N.; Weber, R. J. M.; Van Westen, G. J. P.; Wheelock, C. E.; Williams, A. J.; Witters, H.; Zdrzil, B.; Županič, A.; Willighagen, E. L. ELIXIR and Toxicology: A Community in Development. *F1000Research* **2023**, *10*, 1129. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.74502.2>.
- (12) Rocca-Serra, P.; Gu, W.; Ioannidis, V.; Abbassi-Daloui, T.; Capella-Gutierrez, S.; Chandramouliswaran, I.; Splendiani, A.; Burdett, T.; Giessmann, R. T.; Henderson, D.; Batista, D.; Emam, I.; Gadiya, Y.; Giovanni, L.; Willighagen, E.; Evelo, C.; Gray, A. J. G.; Gribbon, P.; Juty, N.; Welter, D.; Quast, K.; Peeters, P.; Plasterer, T.; Wood, C.; Van Der Horst, E.; Reilly, D.; Van Vlijmen, H.; Scollen, S.; Lister, A.; Thurston, M.; Granell, R.; the FAIR Cookbook Contributors; Backianathan, G.; Baier, S.; Thomsen, A. C.; Cook, M.; Courtot, M.; d'Arcy, M.; Dauth, K.; Del Piico, E. M.; Garcia, L.; Goldmann, U.; Grouès, V.; Clarke, D. J. B.; Lefloch, E.; Liyanage, I.; Papadopoulos, P.; Pommier, C.; Reynares, E.; Ronzano, F.; Delfin-Rossaro, A.; Sagatopam, V.; Sedani, A.; Sedlyarov, V.; Shilova, L.; Singh, S.; Strubel, J.; Van Bochove, K.; Warnes, Z.; Woollard, P.; Xu, F.; Zaliani, A.; Sansone, S.-A. The FAIR Cookbook - the Essential Resource for and by FAIR Doers. *Sci. Data* **2023**, *10* (1), 292. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02166-3>.
- (13) European Commission. Joint Research Centre. *GRACIOUS Data Logging Templates for the Environmental, Health and Safety Assessment of Nanomaterials.*; Publications Office: LU, 2019.
- (14) Kochev, N.; Jeliaskova, N.; Paskaleva, V.; Tancheva, G.; Iliev, L.; Ritchie, P.; Jeliaskov, V. Your Spreadsheets Can Be FAIR: A Tool and FAIRification Workflow for the eNanoMapper Database. *Nanomaterials* **2020**, *10* (10), 1908. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10101908>.